

**glycan
trigger**

D3.2 – In vitro effects of the mucosal glycosylation reprogramming in the control of intestinal ILC module

WP3

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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
CD	Crohn's Disease
FACS	Fluorescence-Activated Cell Sorting
GlcNAc	N-Acetylglucosamine
GnT-V	N-Acetylglucosaminyltransferase V
IBD	Inflammatory Bowel Disease
ILC	Innate Lymphoid Cells
NCR	Natural Cytotoxicity Receptor
ROR	Retinoic Acid-Related Orphan Receptor
UC	Ulcerative Colitis
GBP	Glycan-binding proteins
CTL	C-type lectins

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About the project

GlycanTrigger is a project funded by the European Union, within the Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Actions (RIA). The long-term goal of GlycanTrigger is to unlock a new checkpoint that regulates health to chronic inflammation transition by proposing mucosa glycans modifications as a master switch towards the early perturbation of host-microbial interactions and the consequent activation of both innate and humoral immune systems. Ultimately, we want to intercept or revert this master switch and thereby exploit/analyse whether this constitutes an opportunity to prevent the development of chronic inflammation in at-risk individuals.

Chronic inflammation is the underlying cause of numerous diseases, including Crohn's disease (CD), which may have a preclinical phase with immunological changes occurring before symptoms manifest. To improve disease prediction and prevention, our innovative approach seeks to understand the health-to-intestinal inflammation transition using CD as a disease model. The GlycanTrigger project will investigate when, why and how changes in glycosylation at the surface of the gut mucosa, constitute an early trigger of the health-to-inflammation transition. We will address how changes in glycosylation of the gut mucosa act as a primary event that dysregulates not only local mechanisms, but also systemic mechanisms associated with health to inflammation transition. Although high-risk/high-gain, our project is based on appropriate and long-standing expertise and fundamental biological principles that the consortium has helped establish and is thus likely to lead to (i) breakthrough biomedical concepts in the driving factors that trigger the health to chronic inflammation transition and to (ii) novel predictive tools for early detection of at-risk individuals to develop chronic inflammation, as well as to (iii) a novel intervention strategy that will be tested for disease prevention. In the longer term, the results of GlycanTrigger will improve health literacy through better-informed management of health status, diet and life-style to maintain a healthy gut.

Our strategy for understanding the transition from health to gut inflammation is comprehensive and includes the impact of mucosa glycans on local and systemic mechanisms.

Partners:

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3	SORBONNE	SORBONNE UNIVERSITÉ (France)
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5	GLSMED LH	GLSMED LEARNING HEALTH SA (Portugal)
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6	MOUNT SINAI	ICAHN SCHOOL OF MEDICINE AT MOUNT SINAI (USA)
7	EFCCA	EUROPEAN FEDERATION OF CROHN'S AND ULCERATIVE COLITIS ASSOCIATIONS (Belgium)
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9	LUD	LUDGER LIMITED (United Kingdom)

Executive Summary

Deliverable 3.2 outlines the findings from Work Package 3 (WP3) of the GlycanTrigger project, focusing on Task 3.1 titled, “***The innate lymphoid cells axis triggered by changes in mucosa glycosylation associated with inflammation initiation***”.

In this task, specific glycoengineered mouse models were used and in collaboration with partner Charité Universitätsmedizin Berlin, we here explored the role of host epithelial glycosylation in modulating innate lymphoid cells (ILC) population, investigating the impact of mucosa glycocalyx in the development of ILC3 subset. We explored whether ILCs could display glycan-sensing properties through the expression of C-type lectins (CTLs) at the surface level, and whether this expression could be affected by alterations in mucosal glycosylation. We further explored how ILCs interact with other immune cells using confocal microscopy to evaluate the co-localization of ILCs with other immune cell types. Data presented in this report are preliminary results explored through the collaboration between i3S and Charité Universitätsmedizin Berlin – Institute of Microbiology, Infectious Diseases and Immunology.

Chapter 1

Introduction

1. Introduction

Inflammatory Bowel Disease (IBD), which includes Crohn's disease (CD) and ulcerative colitis (UC), is a complex inflammatory disorder with a significant global burden.[1] The development of effective therapies is challenging due to limited understanding of the events that drive its pathology.[2-4] Nevertheless, impairments in the interaction between gut microbiota and the host immune system have been identified as key contributors to disease onset.[2-4] The intestinal epithelial barrier is essential for preventing excessive contact between microbes and the immune system, and a delicate balance among microbiota, immunity, and barrier function is crucial for intestinal homeostasis. Disruptions in any of these components can lead to functional imbalances and trigger inflammation.[5,6]

Glycans play a central role in regulating immune responses in both health and disease, including IBD and colorectal cancer. The specific influence of glycans on mucosal T cell activity and function has been demonstrated in IBD. Our research has shown that mucosal T lymphocytes from UC patients exhibit a deficiency in branched N-glycosylation, which correlates with disease severity.[7] Notably, ex vivo supplementation of mucosa T cells with N-acetylglucosamine (GlcNAc) enhanced branched N-glycosylation in the T cell receptor (TCR), suppressing proinflammatory responses and regulating T cell activity associated with disease control.[8] Additionally, we observed that Mgat5-deficient mice (lacking the enzyme N-acetylglucosaminyltransferase V (GnT-V), which is responsible for branched N-glycan synthesis) exhibited increased susceptibility to severe colitis. Treatment of Mgat5 KO mice with GlcNAc was able to regulate the intestinal T cell-mediated immune response, associated with decreased disease severity, and suppression of disease progression.[8]

Beyond adaptive immunity, innate lymphoid cells (ILCs) are emerging as key regulators of intestinal homeostasis and inflammation, particularly through their plasticity and ability to produce different cytokines depending on environmental cues. CCR6⁻RORγt⁺ ILC3s, for example, can differentiate into NKp46⁺, IFN-γ-producing cells in a T-bet-dependent manner, protecting the epithelial barrier during infection but potentially contributing to inflammation.[9] Similarly, NKR^{+/-} LTi-like ILCs exhibit a tunable functional program depending on RORγt expression: RORγt⁺ cells produce IL-22 and maintain barrier integrity, whereas RORγt⁻ cells release IFN-γ and can drive colitis, highlighting a direct link between ILC plasticity and IBD pathogenesis.[10] These studies illustrate that ILC fate and function are highly dynamic and responsive to microbiota- and cytokine-derived signals, suggesting that alterations in epithelial glycosylation can influence ILC behaviour and the balance between homeostasis and inflammation.

The role of mucosal glycans in regulating ILCs has recently been explored [11]. However, the molecular mechanisms by which glycans influence ILC function, and whether ILCs in turn modulate other immune cell populations, including B cells, remain largely unexplored. Taking advantage of glycoengineered

mouse models, we here explored whether host epithelial glycosylation shapes ILC populations and whether ILCs are equipped with glycan-sensing properties.

Chapter 2

Methods

2. Methods

2.1 Animals

Mgat5-deficient mice (*Mgat5*^{-/-}) were shipped from i3S (Porto, Portugal) to Charité Universitätsmedizin Berlin – Institute of Microbiology, Infectious Diseases and Immunology (Berlin, Germany). These mice were crossed with a *Rorc*(γ t)-Cre x ROSA26R-eYFP (*ROR* γ t-fate map (fm)), generating the mice *Mgat5*^{-/-} x *ROR* γ t-fm mice. The animals were housed in accordance with the guidelines by the Federation for Laboratory Animal Science Associations and the national animal welfare body *Gesellschaft für Versuchstierkunde*. Experiments were in compliance with the German animal protection law (G0006/23) and were approved by the local animal care committee. All mice used were between 8 to 20 weeks old, unless indicated otherwise. Control mice, littermate controls and experimental mice were assigned randomly, and the sex was not considered in the analysis.

2.2 Isolation of lamina propria leukocytes

The small intestine (SI) and colon of the mice was collected. Peyer's patches were excised and the tissue was cleaned from feces and fat tissue using Ca- and Mg-free PBS. The epithelial layer was dissociated by incubating the cleaned tissue for 15 min at 120 rpm at 37 °C in HBSS supplemented with 5 mM EDTA and 10 mM HEPES. This step was repeated twice. Subsequently, the tissue was minced and incubated for 20 min at 120 rpm at 37 °C in 5 mL of HBSS containing dispase (5 U/ml; BD Biosciences), collagenase D (0.5 mg/ml; Roche) and DNaseA (0.5 mg/ml; Sigma-Aldrich) and 5% FCS. This step was repeated three times for the SI and for Colon it was performed only one time during 45 min. The leukocytes were enriched using a 40/80 Percoll gradient. After enrichment the cells were harvested, washed with FACS buffer (PBS with 10%FCS) and ready to proceed for flow cytometry staining.

2.3 Flow cytometry analysis

All cells analysed by flow cytometry were stained with Fixable Viability Dye (FVD) eFluor™ 780 for viability analysis and exclusion of dead cells. After staining with FVD, surface staining was performed by incubation for 45 minutes at 4°C with surface antibodies (CD45, Lineage (CD5, CD3, TCRb, TCRgd, CD19, Gr1), KLRG1, Nkp46, CD127, NK1.1, CD206, CD207, CD209). Cells analysis was performed on a BD FACS Symphony. Data was analysed using FlowJo software and Prism10.

2.4 Cell sorting for qPCR analysis

For innate lymphoid cell isolation, the SI and colon were collected from *Rorc*^{flm} mice, as previous detailed in section 2.2. After immune cell isolation, cells were staining with surface antibodies (CD45, Lineage, CD11b, KLRG1, NKp46, CD127, NK1.1), followed by staining with Fixable Viability Dye (FVD) eFluor™ 780 for viability analysis and exclusion of dead cells. ILC1, ILC2, ILC3 and myeloid cells were sorted in 350µl of TRIzol™ LS Reagenz (Life Technologies) using BD FACS Aria Fusion.

2.5 Immunofluorescence and confocal microscopy

The SI and Colon were collected from C57BL/6J (WT) and *Mgat5*^{-/-} (KO) mice. For the SI, tissue was subdivided in three portions (duodenum, jejunum and ileum). The tissue was cleaned from feces and fat, cut longitudinally and the swiss-rolling technique was performed. Samples were fixed with periodate-lysine-paraformaldehyde solution overnight at 4 °C. After fixation, the tissue was placed overnight in 30% sucrose. Finally, the tissue was embedded in O.C.T. Tissue Tek (Sakura) and frozen with liquid nitrogen.

For immunofluorescence staining, 12 mm-thick sections were cut using a CM1950 Cryotom (Leica) and placed onto poly-lysine-treated glass slides (ThermoFisher). The slides were dried at room temperature overnight, rehydrated with cold PBS, blocked for 1 h with 10% goat serum (GS) in staining buffer (PBS 1x containing 0.1M Tris, 1%BSA (IgG-free BSA, Sigma), 0.3% Triton-X100). After blocking, the samples were stained with the rabbit anti-mouse ROR gamma (EPR20006), 1:600 dilution in 10% GS in staining buffer, overnight at RT. Following this step, the tissue was washed and incubated with the secondary antibody, goat anti-rabbit IgG Alexa 555 (Invitrogen) 1:600 dilution in 10% GS in staining buffer, during 1h30 at RT. Then, the samples were washed and conjugated primary antibodies (CD3 AF594 1:200, B220 FITC 1:200, IgA Dylight 650 1:200) during 3h at RT. Samples were washed and DAPI staining was performed for 15 min at RT. After staining, the slides were mounted using Invitrogen Prolong Diamonf anti-fade mounting medium and left to dry overnight in the dark. The samples were analyzed using a Stellaris 8 confocal microscope.

Chapter 3

Results

3. Results

3.1 Impaired β 1,6-GlcNAc complex branched *N*-glycosylation leads to a downregulation of ILC3, with increase in NCR⁺ ILC3 in the colon and small intestine

Considering the role of gut mucosa *N*-glycans in intestinal inflammation and colitis severity, we explored their mechanistic influence on intestinal innate lymphoid cells (ILCs). We previously described that alterations in the mucosal glycosylation impacted ILC3 subset in the colon [11]. To further explore the underlying mechanism, we crossed the *Mgat5*^{-/-} mice with a *Rorc*(γ t)-Cre^{Tg} x ROSA26R^{eYFP/+} (ROR γ t-fm) mice, at the Charité Universitätsmedizin Berlin – Institute of Microbiology, Infectious Diseases and Immunology (Andreas Diefenbach Lab). These mice enable to trace ILC3, allowing to check their plasticity in turning into ILC1-like cells (also referred to as ex-ILC3). At steady state, we observed that ILC1 subset was slightly decreased in the colon of *Mgat5*^{-/-} x ROR γ t-fm mice. Additionally, ILC3 population in *Mgat5*^{-/-} x ROR γ t-fm mice was reduced, both in the colon and small intestine (SI) when compared to ROR γ t-fm mice. Among ILC3 subpopulations, the deficiency in branched *N*-glycans specifically affected NCR⁺ ILC3. No differences were observed in ILC2 subset. These results further support that mucosal glycosylation directly impacts the ILC3 population.

Figure 1 Deficiency in mucosa β 1,6-GlcNAc complex branched N-glycosylation leads to an impaired ILC3 at steady-state.

Gating strategy used for the analysis of ILC1, ILC2, ILC3 and the different sub-populations of ILC3 (A). Frequency of ILC1, ILC2 and ILC3 in CD45⁺ cell population in the colon (B-D) and SI (F-H) of ROR γ t-*fm* and *Mgat5*^{-/-} x ROR γ t-*fm* mice, at steady state. Frequency of ILC3 subpopulations (NCR- ILC3, NCR+ ILC3 and ex-ILC3) of total ILC3 in the colon (E) and SI (I) of ROR γ t-*fm* and *Mgat5*^{-/-} x ROR γ t-*fm* mice, at steady state.

Each datapoint represents an individual animal. ROR γ t-*fm*, used as WT controls, are littermate controls. Data is represented as mean \pm SD. Statistical analysis was done using Mann–Whitney test.

3.2 Alterations in host mucosa glycosylation may promote the increase expression of selected C-type lectins on innate lymphoid cells

Glycans can act as ligands for glycan-binding proteins (GBPs), including C-type lectins (CTLs), highlighting their role as key components in immune-regulatory circuits and in the balance between immune activation and immune suppression. CTL receptors are mainly expressed by myeloid cells, playing crucial roles in immune recognition and modulation of immune responses. The downstream signalling pathways orchestrate a spectrum of cellular responses, affecting processes including phagocytosis, cytokine production, and antigen presentation. Their expression and role on ILCs remain unexplored. In this study, we hypothesise that changes in mucosal glycosylation could impact the expression of CTLs on ILCs, enabling them to respond to these glycan structures.

Our preliminary findings suggest that ILCs may express CTLs. Specifically, *Mgat5*^{-/-} x ROR γ t-fm mice appears to upregulate the expression of C-type lectin 1, mainly on ILC2 and ILC3, both in the colon (Figure 2A) and SI (Figure 2B), without statistical significance. In the colon, within the different subsets of ILC3, NCR⁺ ILC3 from *Mgat5*^{-/-} x ROR γ t-fm mice show a higher expression of this receptor. In contrast, in the SI, ex-ILC3 display an increased expression of this marker. In general, ILCs show a low expression on CTLs. However, this expression appears to be modulated by the different mucosal glycans and expressed differently among the different subsets, suggesting a potential role of these receptors in modulating ILCs immune response. Validation of the expression levels on ILCs is now ongoing. Sorting of the different ILCs subsets (Figure 2C) was already performed to validate the expression of a wide range of CTLs.

Complementary, scRNAseq was performed on sorted ILCs (at Charite) and the glycotranscriptomic profile alongside the GBP are now being analysed.

Figure 2 C-type lectins (CTLs) expression in the different ILCs subsets in RORγt-fm (WT control) and Mgat5^{-/-} x RORγt-fm mice

Frequency of C-type lectin 1 in the different ILCs subsets in RORγt-fm and Mgat5^{-/-} x RORγt-fm mice in the colon (A) and SI (B). Sorting strategy for ILC1/ex-ILC3 (CD45+NK1.1+), ILC2 (CD45+NK1.1-CD127+KLRG1+), ILC3 (CD45+NK1.1-CD127+YFP+) and myeloid cells (CD45+NK1.1-CD11b+) (C). Each datapoint represents an individual animal. Data is represented as mean ± SD. Mann–Whitney test was performed.

3.3 Evaluation of the co-localization of ILCs and other immune cells

In this task, we also aim to determine whether ILCs can interact with other immune cells triggered by changes in mucosal glycosylation. Using WT and *Mgat5*^{-/-} mice, we performed immunofluorescence of different immune cell markers such as B220 (B cells), IgA, CD3 (T cells) and ROR γ t. The images suggest that in cryptopatches (Figure 3A) other immune cells are sitting together with ILC3 (positive for ROR γ t and negative for CD3), as also observed in peyer patches (Figure 3B). The impact of the mucosal glycosylation is currently being assessed by exploring WT and *Mgat5*^{-/-} mice (duodenum, jejunum, ileum and colon).

Figure 3 Immunofluorescence of B cells, T cells, IgA, and ILC3 in SI samples

Representative confocal microscopy images of cryptopatches (CPs) (A) and peyer patches (PPs) (B) from the SI of WT mice. Sections were stained for the indicated markers (20x).

Chapter 4

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4. References

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Chapter 5

Final Remarks

5. Final Remarks

Our preliminary results explore for the first time the hypothesis that ILCs can sense glycans in a direct way, through the expression of CTLs. We show that a decrease in β 1,6-GlcNAc complex branched *N*-glycosylation lead to a decrease in ILC3, both in the colon and SI, suggesting that mucosal glycosylation have a direct impact on ILCs. The specific mechanisms by which mucosa glycosylation dictates ILC-associated immunity, including how it influences CTL expression, will be further investigated. Moreover, we have further exploited how ILCs interact with other immune cells, and additional *in vitro* and *in vivo* assays will be performed to understand if these axis can impact immunopathogenesis of the disease.

Overall, this work will contribute to a better understanding of the sequence of events associated with health-to-inflammation transition, aiming to pinpoint glycans as novel therapeutic targets for IBD prevention.

